

Conditions Shaping Induction Stove Purchase Intention in Indonesia: A Fuzzy-Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis

Najwa Mumtaz

Industrial Engineering Study Program, Sebelas Maret University, Jebres,
Surakarta, 57121 - 57162, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1303-993X>

***Retno Wulan Damayanti**

Industrial Engineering Study Program, Sebelas Maret University, Jebres,
Surakarta, 57121 - 57162, Indonesia
Center of Technology Development and Industrial Collaboration, Institute for Research and
Community Service, Sebelas Maret University, Jebres, Surakarta, 57121 - 57162, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5779-3337>

*Corresponding author email: rwd@ft.uns.ac.id; retnowulan@staff.uns.ac.id

Fitria Dinda Kartika

Industrial Engineering Study Program, Sebelas Maret University, Jebres,
Surakarta, 57121 - 57162, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1979-841X>

Haryono Setiadi

Informatics and Science Data Study Program, Sebelas Maret University, Jebres,
Surakarta, 57121 - 57162, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6394-0548>

Abstract

Background: Indonesia's clean energy policy integration includes the transition from liquefied propane gas (LPG) to induction stoves. The Indonesian government is targeting the conversion of induction stoves in 8.2 million households by 2025; however, actual uptake remains at 0.3%.

Objective: This study examines the factors and conditions influencing Indonesian households' intentions to adopt and purchase induction stoves. By identifying these key determinants, the research aims to provide comprehensive insights into the behavioural drivers of the adoption of clean cooking technologies in Indonesia.

Methodology: This research uses a fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) to analyse survey responses from 515 eligible Indonesian respondents. The study examines eight condition variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence,

facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, price value, environmental knowledge, and policy measures. Data were calibrated into fuzzy sets and analysed with fsQCA 4.1.

Results: The analysis reveals three distinct combinations of factors that consistently lead to high purchase intention, and two configurations associated with low intention. High purchase intention occurred only when three factors (performance expectancy, hedonic motivation, and policy measures) were present, regardless of configuration. In contrast, low intention was consistently associated with the absence of multiple key factors, even when environmental concern and policy support were present. These findings clarify the need for specific conditions and highlight the interplay among factors shaping household intentions.

Conclusion: Successfully implementing induction stoves in Indonesia requires comprehensive and collaborative interventions. Rather than relying on a single policy or promotional strategy, initiatives must focus on usability, motivation, infrastructure, and policy.

Unique Contribution: This study applies fsQCA to capture causal complexity beyond linear models, identifying essential enabling conditions—performance expectancy, hedonic drive, and policy support—to inform focused actions. This study extends the application of fsQCA to the clean energy sector, focusing on the underexplored area of low-cost clean cooking technologies in emerging economies.

Key Recommendations: Future studies should integrate fsQCA with complementary methods such as structural equation modeling (SEM) to validate causal directions and enhance generalizability. Longitudinal designs are needed to track how intention evolves into actual adoption, while qualitative approaches can help uncover unmeasured contextual conditions—such as electricity reliability or financial resilience—that may explain contradictory pathways.

Keywords: Purchase Intention; Induction Stove; fsQCA; Clean Cooking Technology; Technology Adoption

Introduction

Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) is widely used for cooking and heating due to its high thermal efficiency; however, as a fossil-based fuel, its extensive consumption inevitably contributes to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and combustion-related health concerns. In 2007, Indonesia implemented a kerosene-to-LPG conversion program that expanded household access to modern cooking energy; however, this policy also increased reliance on imports. National LPG consumption rose from 5.6 million tons in 2013 to 8.7 million tons in 2022, while domestic production declined slightly to 1.9 million tons in 2023 (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Republic of Indonesia, 2023). The resulting import gap of 6.9 million tons imposed a significant fiscal burden, with annual subsidies estimated at 60-70 trillion Indonesian rupiah (INR).

Dependence on LPG has various implications, including environmental impacts, as household LPG use emits carbon. The Indonesian government has pursued several alternative policies to address this issue, such as promoting the use of electric-based cooking technology (induction stoves). This approach also aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG 7) and the national commitment to achieve the target of New and Renewable Energy (NRE) by 2060 (Prasojo & Hartono, 2023). Induction stoves have several advantages, such as a high thermal efficiency of 87.78% and lower carbon emissions when powered by NRE. Thus, the state-owned power company, PT Indonesia Electricity Company. PLN (Persero), has launched several programs to replace household LPG use with induction

stoves, targeting 8.2 million households by 2025 and 58 million by 2050.

Despite the Indonesian government's efforts, household use of induction stoves remains relatively low, with usage at around 0.3% of households (Damayanti et al., 2024). Further implementation challenges include the relatively high initial purchase price, concerns about rising electricity costs, and diverse socio-economic conditions across Indonesia. Thus, efforts to transition to induction stoves (clean energy) depend on technical feasibility and economic incentives, as well as other behavioural, social, and contextual factors that influence household decision-making.

Given these complex barriers, addressing adoption dynamics requires analytical methods that consider interdependent, context-specific causal relationships; however, most current studies rely on linear statistical models, such as structural equation modelling (SEM). These approaches assume additive, symmetric relationships, limiting the ability to detect causal asymmetry and multiple, equally sufficient pathways to a given outcome (Falisa & Tricahyono, 2025; Damayanti et al., 2024); therefore, critical combinations of behavioural, economic, and policy factors are overlooked, leading to overly simplified interpretations of household adoption.

This study addresses a critical research gap in the literature: most analyses of household adoption of induction stoves in Indonesia overlook the causal complexity and rely primarily on linear models. To strengthen our main argument, we propose using fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) to identify specific combinations of behavioural, economic, and policy factors that collectively shape adoption. FsQCA enhances understanding by capturing causal asymmetry and equifinality (Pappas & Woodside, 2021) while accommodating the diverse realities of Indonesian households. This study aims to clarify how multiple, intersecting factors contribute to high and low intentions to adopt induction stoves. The findings can provide a more nuanced understanding of household decision-making regarding Indonesia's clean energy transition.

Theoretical Background

Induction Stove: Clean Cooking Technology

Induction stoves represent a promising clean-cooking technology, offering significantly higher energy efficiency and lower emissions than traditional LPG and electric stoves. A recent comparative study found that induction cooktops achieve cooking efficiencies of 81%–90%, substantially higher than the approximately 40% of gas stoves, due to direct electromagnetic heating of cookware (Damayanti et al., 2024). Their zero-combustion operation also reduces indoor air pollutants and GHG emissions, making them a health- and climate-sensitive solution, especially when powered by NRE.

Pilot studies in Indonesia have shown that induction stoves outperform LPG and conventional electric stoves in reducing operational costs and carbon footprints (Damayanti et al., 2024). Initial implementation challenges include higher acquisition costs and the need for compatible cookware; however, the widespread promotion of induction stoves aligns with global strategies to reduce household air pollution and facilitate sustainable energy transitions, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Hakam et al., 2022).

Purchase Intention and Adoption of Technology

Purchase intention refers to an individual's plan to buy a product. It is widely recognised as a key predictor of technology adoption (Falisa & Tricahyono, 2025), reflecting a consumer's assessment of value, usability, and motivation before making actual purchasing decisions.

Regarding technology adoption, purchase intention bridges awareness and usage, especially when adoption requires behavioural change and infrastructure support (Jain et al., 2022). Many studies have shown that effective adoption of electric vehicles, smart appliances, and digital platforms is associated with perceived usefulness, hedonic value, and social norms (Phung et al., 2020).

Regarding induction stoves, purchase intention is crucial for the adoption of clean cooking. Although the Indonesian government supports the technology, adoption rates remain low. Recent studies have shown that a strong desire to purchase—alongside price, availability, and trust in the technology—is a powerful predictor of continued use (Damayanti et al., 2024; Prasajo & Hartono, 2023). This intention must be strengthened to make long-term changes in home energy use.

Fuzzy-Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (FsQCA)

FsQCA is a configurational method that identifies how combinations of conditions lead to specific outcomes. Unlike correction models, fsQCA can handle causal complexity, recognising that different combinations of factors can yield the same outcome. Technology adoption research is increasingly using this approach to investigate how behavioural, contextual, and policy-related factors interact (Pappas & Woodside, 2021).

FsQCA is particularly useful for studies of household energy use, as decisions vary with an individual's social and economic circumstances. By identifying multiple causal pathways, fsQCA provides insight into the drivers of behavioural intention and complements traditional methods such as SEM (Misangyi et al., 2017).

Methods

Conceptual Model

Figure 1 illustrates the interrelationships among eight conditions that may influence household purchase intention toward induction stoves: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, hedonic motivation, price value, facilitating conditions, social influence, policy measures, and perceived environmental knowledge.

This model does not assume linear and additive relationships; instead, it adopts a configurational perspective consistent with the fsQCA approach (Ragin, 2008; Fiss, 2011). Including these constructs draws on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT2) and extended behavioural models that emphasise contextual and policy factors relevant to sustainable technology adoption (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Pappas & Woodside, 2021). This framework allows us to explore multiple, equally sufficient pathways—known as equifinality—leading to both high and low purchase intention.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of Induction Stove Purchase Intention

This study uses fsQCA because it is particularly well-suited to analysing complex social phenomena, such as technology adoption, in which different combinations of social, psychological, and contextual factors can yield similar behavioural intentions. Each construct in the conceptual model is treated as a causal condition, and we examine how different combinations of these conditions are associated with household purchase intention.

The analytical procedure comprises four main stages: (1) fuzzy calibration of raw data into membership scores ranging from 0 to 1, (2) construction of a truth table, (3) Boolean minimisation, and (4) necessary condition analysis. These steps identify distinct configurations of conditions associated with high and low purchase intentions.

The fsQCA methodology recognises that purchase intention emerges from a combination of interacting factors rather than a single determinant, making it appropriate for this analysis. Different consumer segments may exhibit unique combinations of conditions, enabling targeted policy and marketing strategies that support governments and manufacturers in promoting clean energy transitions through the adoption of induction stoves. Table 1 presents the operational definitions of the condition factors employed in this study.

Table 1. Operational Definition and Indicators of Induction Stove Purchase Intention

Attribute	Operational Definition	Indicator	References
Effort Expectancy (EE)	User perception of how easy it is to use induction stoves as a new technology	- Ease of learning - Ease of operation - Clarity of use	(Jain et al., 2022; Venkatesh et al., 2012)
Performance Expectancy (PE)	Perception that induction stoves improve cooking performance	- Usefulness - Efficiency - Productivity	

Social Influence (SI)	Perception that others encourage their use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social norm - Social trend - Peer perception
Facilitating Condition (FC)	Perception that support and infrastructure are available	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service availability - Infrastructure support - Incentive facility
Hedonic Motivation (HM)	User perception of enjoyment when using induction stoves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enjoyment - Comfort - Safety
Price Value (PV)	User perception of the trade-off between the benefits and costs of using induction stoves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Price importance - Value for money - Sustainability value
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (PEK)	User perception of environmental awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pollution awareness - Fossil fuel alternative - Environmental responsibility - Environmental awareness
Policy Measures (PM)	Perception of government incentive policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy incentive type - Subsidy amount - Economic benefit
Purchase Intention (PI)	Intention to purchase induction stoves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feature preference - Purchase likelihood - Environmental motivation - Price tolerance

Research Instrument

This study uses a structured questionnaire, with items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree), to analyse the effects of eight condition factors on the purchase intention for induction stoves. The instrument established the face and construct validity, with all factor loadings exceeding 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010). Reliability is confirmed using Cronbach’s alpha. All values exceed 0.70, indicating acceptable internal consistency; therefore, all items of the indicator instrument were valid and reliable.

Study Design and Population

This study employs a quantitative cross-sectional design using an online survey method. This design was selected to capture a comprehensive snapshot of household purchase intentions and the associated behavioural factors at a single point in time.

The population of this study comprises Indonesian citizens who are potential adopters of clean cooking technology. Specifically, the target population includes individuals aged 18 years or older who currently possess cooking experience using conventional stoves (LPG) and have no prior experience with purchasing or using induction stoves. These criteria

ensured that the responses reflected genuine purchase intentions rather than post-usage evaluations.

Data Collection and Analysis

Purposive sampling was used to distribute the structured questionnaire. Data screening was conducted on 527 initial responses to eliminate incomplete answers and ensure compliance with the established criteria; the final dataset comprised 515 complete and valid responses suitable for analysis. The analysis stages include fuzzy calibration of raw data (0 to 1 membership scores), construction of a truth table, Boolean minimisation, and necessary condition analysis. These steps allow for identifying distinct factor combinations associated with high or low purchase intention.

Data analysis proceeded using the fsQCA 4.1 software. Before data calibration, the first stage of data analysis involved data aggregation using Microsoft Excel 365. Aggregation was carried out by calculating the average value of each indicator within its corresponding construct, resulting in a single composite score for each variable per respondent.

Result

Fuzzy Calibration

A calibration process was applied to convert the composite scores into fuzzy membership values. Using the direct calibration method, the thresholds were set at 0.05 for non-membership, 0.95 for full membership, and 0.50 as the cross-over point (Ragin, 2008). To determine these fuzzy thresholds, the distribution of each variable was examined based on its deviation and range (Ragin, 2008; Rihoux & Ragin, 2009). The fuzzy-set anchors may be established using the maximum and minimum values for full and non-membership and the midpoint for the cross-over (Damayanti et al., 2021). This calibration mechanism was applied in the present study, and the resulting fuzzy thresholds are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Fuzzy Membership Threshold of Induction Stove Purchase Intention

	EE	PE	SI	FC	HM	PV	PEK	PM	PI
Full Membership	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Cross over	4.26	4.35	4.12	4.35	4.49	4.34	4.49	4.45	4.25
Non-Full Membership	2.33	1.00	1.00	1.67	1.00	1.00	2.50	1.67	1.50

Raw consistency indicates the reliability with which each combination yields the desired outcome (Phung et al., 2020). This study includes 515 cases; therefore, the frequency threshold was set at five and the consistency threshold at 0.90.

The number and level of detail differ between the truth table and the final fsQCA solution due to the logical minimisation process (Boolean minimisation). The fsQCA algorithm combines two or more rows of the truth table into a single, simplified configuration when they differ in only one condition but produce the same outcome.

This Boolean minimisation procedure reduces complexity and identifies the most parsimonious configurations that account for the outcome, thereby facilitating a more straightforward interpretation of the causal relationships among conditions.

Truth Table

The minimum recommended consistency threshold is 0.75; however, a higher minimum threshold of 0.85 is suggested for datasets with more than 150 cases to ensure analytical rigour. This study includes 515 cases; thus, the frequency threshold was set at five and the consistency threshold at 0.90, both of which exceed the recommended minimum levels.

The truth table displayed all possible configurations in binary format; full membership conditions (fuzzy values > 0.5) were coded as “1” (presence), and non-full membership conditions (≤ 0.5) as “0” (absence). The analysis examined high purchase intention (fPI) and low purchase intention (\sim fPI); “ \sim ” denotes the negation of the condition.

The solution configurations were formulated using the Quine–McCluskey algorithm (QMC) for Boolean minimisation. Three solution configurations were identified for the high purchase intention (presented in Table 3). The solution coverage value is 0.724189, indicating that all configurations collectively explain 72.42% of the observed data. Meanwhile, the solution consistency value of 0.984912 suggests that approximately 98.49% of the cases represented by these configurations are effectively explained.

Table 3. Final Configurations for High Purchase Intention for Induction Stoves

High Purchase Intention			
Configuration		Raw Coverage	Raw Consistency
1	fEE*fPE*fSI*fFC*fHM*fPEK*fPM	0.674082	0.987154
2	fEE*fPE*fFC*fHM*fPV*fPEK*fPM	0.685396	0.983805
3	fPE*fSI*fFC*fHM*fPV*fPEK*fPM	0.707453	0.984215

Two solution configurations were identified for the low purchase intention shown in Table 4. The solution coverage value is 0.477414, indicating that all configurations collectively explain 47.74% of the observed data. Meanwhile, the solution consistency value of 0.968411 indicates that approximately 96.84% of the cases represented by these configurations are effectively explained.

Table 4. Final Configuration for Low Purchase Intention for Induction Stoves

Low Purchase Intention			
Configuration		Raw Coverage	Raw Consistency
1	\sim fEE* \sim fPE* \sim fFC* \sim fHM* \sim fPV* \sim fPEK* \sim fPM	0.447616	0.97936
2	\sim fEE* \sim fPE* \sim fSI* \sim fFC* \sim fHM* \sim fPV*fPEK*fPM	0.31869	0.970807

Necessary Conditions

The final analysis stage identified causal conditions that must be present, with consistency values ≥ 0.90 for the outcome, termed necessary conditions. Three conditions are necessary for high purchase intention (fPI): performance expectancy (fPE) (0.900873), hedonic motivation (fHM) (0.930748), and policy measures (fPM) (0.905037). No necessary conditions for low purchase intention (\sim fPI) were identified, as none met the required consistency threshold of ≥ 0.90 .

Discussion

High Purchase Intention

Functional and Psychological Drivers

Three configurations are associated with high purchase intention. These configurations consistently demonstrate that strong functional and psychological factors are the primary drivers of induction stove adoption. Key factors such as performance expectancy, hedonic motivation, and policy measures appear in all solution paths, indicating that consumers' willingness to adopt is fundamentally driven by the perception that the technology is useful, enjoyable, and supported by government incentives.

The first three configurations demonstrate that strong functional and psychological factors drive high purchase intention toward induction stoves. These factors include performance expectancy, hedonic motivation, and policy measures, which consistently emerge as key determinants of consumers' willingness to adopt. Other conditions, such as effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, price value, and social influence, vary or are inconsistently high. In contrast, the intention to purchase remains strong when consumers perceive induction stoves as functioning efficiently, being easy to use, and providing an enjoyable cooking experience.

Overall, the UTAUT2 model identifies performance expectancy as a dominant determinant of behavioural intention, emphasising the central role of perceived usefulness and convenience (Venkatesh et al., 2012). When consumers perceive that the new technology enhances cooking efficiency and quality, this perception incentivises the transition from conventional stoves to induction cookers. This aligns with the theoretical premise that for utilitarian appliances, the capability to perform the primary task effectively is often a more critical driver of adoption than the mere ease of operation.

From a psychological perspective, hedonic motivation plays an important role, reflecting the enjoyment, satisfaction, and pride derived from using a modern, innovative appliance. This emotional engagement shapes positive attitudes and adds intrinsic value, reinforcing consumers' purchase intentions. Consistent with established technology acceptance models, intrinsic motivation complements functional utility (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Furthermore, policy measures and perceived environmental knowledge can extend consumer motivation beyond the individual level. For example, government incentives, energy-efficiency campaigns, and promotional initiatives for environmentally friendly products can increase awareness and a sense of responsibility regarding sustainable consumption (Phung et al., 2020).

Collectively, these factors suggest that a single dimension does not drive consumers' intention to adopt induction stoves. Instead, it results from a combination of functional performance, psychological satisfaction, and institutional reinforcement. Consumers are motivated by practical benefits, emotional engagement, and external validation, which together strengthen their confidence and decision to purchase.

The Reinforcing Role of Social Influence

Unlike previous assumptions where social pressure alone might drive adoption in collectivist cultures, these research findings suggest that social influence functions primarily as a reinforcing mechanism rather than a stand-alone driver. Social influence appears as a core

condition in Configuration 1 and Configuration 3, always in combination with high performance expectancy and hedonic motivation.

This pattern implies that while social endorsement—from family, peers, or community leaders—is crucial in the Indonesian context, it is most effective when the technology is also perceived as functionally superior and emotionally satisfying. In these pathways, social norms likely serve to validate the consumer's decision, reducing the perceived risk associated with switching from LPG to induction stoves. This aligns with the view that in high power-distance societies (Hofstede, 2001), social approval acts as a catalyst that accelerates the adoption of technologies already deemed useful (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

Interestingly, the absence of social influence in Configuration 2 suggests that peer support is not strictly mandatory if other economic and infrastructure factors are compelling. In Configuration 2, the combination of Price Value (PV) and Facilitating Conditions (FC)—alongside Performance Expectation (PE) and Hedonic Motivation (HM)—is sufficient to drive intention even without explicit social pressure. This indicates the existence of a more "pragmatic" consumer segment that prioritizes economic value and infrastructure readiness over social trends. However, for the majority of pathways (Configurations 1 and 3), the synergy between social validation and functional utility remains a dominant force. Therefore, marketing strategies should not rely on influencers or community leaders in isolation. Instead, social campaigns should be designed to explicitly endorse the utility and enjoyment of the product, thereby linking social credibility directly to the stove's functional performance.

Low Purchase Intention

Two configurations are associated with low purchase intention. Initially, all key variables—effort expectancy, performance expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, and price value—are low. This outcome indicates that when consumers perceive the product as challenging to use, ineffective, lacking social endorsement, inconvenient, unexciting, or expensive, their purchase intention drops significantly. Consistent with established adoption models (Venkatesh et al., 2012), this implies that without functional (usefulness, convenience) and emotional (joy, value perception) motivators, even supported technologies may fail to maintain user interest.

The second configuration shows that even when environmental knowledge and policy measures are high, low levels of effort expectancy, performance expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, hedonic motivation, and price value are associated with low purchase intention. Environmental awareness and policy incentives alone cannot overcome negative perceptions about core product attributes. Phung et al. (2020), using fsQCA in the context of e-commerce adoption, showed that environmental awareness and institutional support trigger intention only when combined with factors such as product value and credibility. For others, functional and conditional values such as price, convenience, and product quality can shape consumption choices more heavily; thus, environmental concern and policy support cannot shift behaviour unless consumers see clear individual benefits. Additionally, underlying psychological barriers may exist, such as status quo bias and anxiety over change, which deter consumers despite external motivations. These hidden anxieties may stem from fear of the unknown or concerns about mastering new technologies, underscoring the need for initiatives that alleviate these emotional burdens and reassure consumers about the transition.

These configurations indicate that low purchase intention results from the absence or weakness of multiple factors. Environmental knowledge and policy support are positive influences; however, they are insufficient without complementary motivators such as ease of use, perceived benefits, positive peer influence, and value for money. Certain necessary conditions shape high purchase intention; conversely, low purchase intention stems from a collective lack of reinforcing elements. Thus, future efforts to promote induction stoves must address multiple enabling conditions; focusing on only one or two will likely be insufficient to influence consumer behaviour in Indonesia.

Limitations and Future Research

This study provides valuable insights into the adoption of sustainable technologies in emerging economies. It also supports Indonesia's clean energy transition and climate commitments; however, several limitations must be addressed to inform future research directions. First, although fsQCA is an appropriate method for examining causal complexity, it is not designed for statistical generalisation or hypothesis testing (Ragin, 2008; Fiss, 2011). The configurations identified in this study, therefore, reflect context-specific causal pathways rather than universal causal laws. While these findings provide meaningful insights into the behavioural patterns of Indonesian households, they should not be interpreted as generalizable to all populations or settings. To address this limitation, future research may combine fsQCA with complementary methods such as SEM or regression. Such hybrid approaches would allow researchers to test the statistical significance of direct effects and assess the extent to which the identified configurational patterns can be generalised across broader populations (Damayanti et al., 2021).

Second, although this study included a diverse set of respondents, the data were collected via self-reported online surveys. This may introduce response bias and underrepresent households with limited or unreliable internet access. In addition, the survey design is cross-sectional, meaning that responses were collected at a single point in time. As a result, the data do not capture temporal dynamics or changes in respondents' perceptions, and therefore cannot provide insights into how purchase intention may evolve into actual adoption. To address this limitation, future research could employ longitudinal panel designs to observe changes in intention and behaviour over time, providing stronger evidence on the intention-behaviour relationship. Furthermore, qualitative approaches, such as interviews or focus group discussions, would help uncover unmeasured contextual moderators—such as electricity reliability, trust in government incentives, or household financial resilience—that may explain contradictory or divergent configurations observed in fsQCA results.

Conclusions

This study applies fsQCA to examine the complex configurations that influence the purchase intentions for induction cooktops among Indonesian households. The findings reveal three pathways leading to high purchase intentions and two pathways leading to low purchase intentions, confirming that multiple concurrent conditions drive technology adoption. Performance expectancy, hedonic motivation, and policy measures were key factors for high purchase intention, underscoring the importance of perceived functional benefits, an enjoyable user experience, and strong policy support.

These findings provide two main insights. First, distinct combinations of factors may motivate different consumer segments, enabling more targeted marketing and policy

strategies. Second, the identified necessary conditions provide clear guidance for prioritising improvements in product performance, user experience, and supporting policies. This finding suggests that policymakers should focus on integrated interventions rather than isolated efforts. Moreover, the significance of hedonic motivation indicates that emphasising the enjoyable aspects of induction cooking could enhance adoption. Promoting tangible benefits like energy efficiency and cost savings can provide crucial support for manufacturers and marketers. At the same time, the varied role of social influence across configurations suggests that peer-to-peer marketing is effective for specific segments.

In contrast, low purchase intention was associated with the absence or weakness of multiple key factors, including effort expectancy, performance expectancy, social influence, and price value. Notably, when present, environmental awareness and policy support were insufficient to drive intention without accompanying perceptions of usability, benefit, and affordability. This result emphasises that adoption requires a comprehensive alignment of enabling conditions; positive attitudes alone are insufficient. Thus, overcoming resistance to adoption requires policymakers and stakeholders to adopt a multidimensional approach that simultaneously addresses functional, emotional, and contextual barriers.

Data Availability Statement

The data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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